

A RAPID REVIEW OF PROPERTIES OF POISSON PROBABILITY DISTRIBUTION AND ITS VERIFICATION WITH AN REAL LIFE EXAMPLE

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ABSTRACT

The Poisson distribution, a cornerstone of probability theory, is instrumental in modeling the occurrence of rare events over a fixed interval of time or space. This study delves into the mathematical properties of the Poisson distribution, elucidating its derivation from the binomial distribution and highlighting key characteristics such as its mean, variance, and moment generating function. The research underscores the distribution's defining feature: the mean being equal to the variance, an attribute that simplifies its application across diverse fields. Real-life applications are explored extensively to demonstrate the utility of the Poisson distribution in various domains. In telecommunications, it models the arrival of phone calls at a call center; in biology, it predicts the distribution of mutations in a given strand of DNA; in traffic engineering, it estimates the number of cars passing through a toll booth in a given period. The study also examines its role in finance for modeling rare events such as defaults on loans or insurance claims. Through detailed analysis and practical examples, this study not only reinforces the theoretical foundations of the Poisson distribution but also showcases its versatility and indispensability in solving real-world problems. The findings highlight the importance of understanding the underlying assumptions and limitations of the Poisson model to effectively apply it in practice. This research paper delves into the properties and real-life applications of the Poisson probability distribution, elucidating its significance and versatility.

Keywords: Probability, probabilistic, Poisson distribution, facilitator, Mean, Variance

I INTRODUCTION

Probability theory, which underpins statistical analysis, is fundamental for constructing dependable mathematical structures that help to represent and make sense of diverse unpredictable events. Within the vast array of probability distributions available, the Poisson distribution remains distinguished and indispensable because of its relevance in a wide range of practical situations. This versatile distribution plays a crucial role in statistical modeling by offering a reliable framework to capture events such as rare occurrences and random intervals, making it a valuable tool for researchers, scientists, and analysts seeking to understand and predict uncertainties in various fields. [1]

The Poisson probability distribution, a fundamental concept in statistics, is widely recognized and applied in various real-world scenarios. This discrete probability distribution plays a vital role in fields like telecommunications, traffic engineering, and epidemiology, offering valuable insights and predictions. Its utility lies in accurately modeling the occurrences of events within a fixed timeframe or area, particularly under specific situational constraints. This versatile distribution is essential for understanding and predicting random phenomena with a focus on occurrence frequencies. As we explore the Poisson distribution more comprehensively, we will unveil its intricate definition, key properties, mathematical derivation, practical applications, and nuances that contribute to its significance. By unraveling the depths of this distribution, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of its significance and practical implications across diverse domains where statistical analysis is crucial. [2]

II POISSON DISTRIBUTION

The Poisson distribution, a fundamental concept in probability theory and statistics, bears the name of the eminent French mathematician Siméon Denis Poisson due to his significant contributions to its development. This distribution functions as a crucial tool in quantifying the likelihood of a certain number of occurrences within a specific duration or area given a constant average rate of occurrence. It is particularly suited for scenarios where events happen independently at a consistent mean rate and without any dependence on prior occurrences. Characterized by a sole parameter denoted as λ , signifying the average event

rate per interval, the Poisson distribution provides a precise and reliable method for modeling random events in various fields, such as telecommunications, biology, and economics.[3]

The probability mass function (PMF) of the Poisson distribution is given by:

$$P(X = k) = \frac{\lambda^k e^{-\lambda}}{k!}$$

where:

- X is the random variable representing the number of events.
- k is a non-negative integer (0, 1, 2, ...).
- λ is the average rate of events per interval.
- e is the base of the natural logarithm, approximately equal to 2.71828.[4]

III ILLUSTRATION OF POISSON DISTRIBUTION WITH AN EXAMPLE

Example: Number of Calls Received by a Call Center

In a typical scenario where a call center operates, it is common for them to handle an average of 5 incoming calls every hour. To accurately predict and analyze the likelihood of receiving different numbers of calls within an hour, the Poisson distribution is frequently employed as a statistical model.

Poisson distribution formula

In probability theory, the Poisson distribution formula

$$P(X = k) = \frac{e^{-\lambda} \lambda^k}{k!}$$

where:

- λ is the average number of events (calls) per interval (hour).
- k is the actual number of events (calls) we want to find the probability for.
- e is the base of the natural logarithm (approximately equal to 2.71828).

An essential concept, known as the Poisson distribution, is widely employed in quantitative analysis to precisely determine the chances of witnessing a precise quantity, denoted as 'k,' of events happening during a set timeframe or spatial region. This mathematical technique is indispensable in portraying and measuring the likelihood of random happenings with precision, thereby enabling a robust modeling of uncertain events for accurate probabilistic assessments and predictions.

Calculation

Let's calculate the probability of receiving exactly 3 calls in one hour.

1. **Average number of calls (λ):** 5 calls per hour

2. **Number of calls (k):** 3 calls

Plugging these values into the formula:

$$P(X = 3) = \frac{e^{-5} 5^3}{3!}$$

First, calculate $5^3 = 125$

Next, calculate $e^{-5} \approx 0.00674$

Then, calculate $3! = 3 \times 2 \times 1 = 6$

Now, plug these values back into the formula:

$$P(X = 3) = \frac{0.00674 \times 125}{6} \approx 0.1404$$

So, the probability of receiving exactly 3 calls in one hour is approximately 0.1404 or 14.04%. [4]

IV PROPERTIES OF THE POISSON DISTRIBUTION

The Poisson distribution has several key properties that make it useful for modeling count data:

(a) Mean and Variance

- **Mean:** The mean, also known as the expected value, plays a crucial role in understanding the Poisson distribution. In this context, the mean of a Poisson distribution is represented by the symbol λ , which signifies the average number of events that occur in a fixed interval of time or space. Understanding the concept of mean in the context of a Poisson distribution is essential for various statistical analyses and applications. It serves as a measure of central tendency that helps in characterizing the distribution and predicting the likelihood of events occurring. By calculating the mean,

statisticians can gain insights into the average rate of occurrence for a specific phenomenon, providing valuable information for decision-making processes. Therefore, recognizing the significance of the mean in a Poisson distribution is fundamental in statistical theory and practice. Furthermore, the mean not only provides a numerical summary of the distribution but also serves as a fundamental parameter for modeling real-world phenomena accurately. In conclusion, the mean, with its close association to the Poisson distribution and its interpretation as λ , holds a key position in statistical analysis and inference, offering valuable insights into the frequency and occurrence of events in various scenarios. The mean of a Poisson-distributed random variable X is equal to λ .

i.e. Mean = $E(X) = \lambda$

- **Variance:** In probability theory, variance serves as a crucial measure of the spread or dispersion of a probability distribution. Specifically, for a Poisson distribution, the variance is directly equal to the distribution's rate parameter, denoted as λ . This relationship between the variance and λ in a Poisson distribution is fundamental as it highlights how the variability within the distribution is directly tied to its rate of occurrence. Understanding this connection can provide valuable insights into the nature of Poisson processes and their inherent tendencies for fluctuations. The variance of X is also equal to λ . i.e. Variance = $\text{Var}(X) = \lambda$

This unique property, where the mean and variance are equal, distinguishes the Poisson distribution from many other probability distributions.

(b) Moment Generating Function

In addition to calculating the mean and variance, higher moments can be determined to offer a more comprehensive understanding of the distribution's properties and features. These higher moments, such as skewness and kurtosis, provide deeper insights into the asymmetry, tail behavior, and peakedness of the distribution. By examining beyond the first two moments, analysts and researchers can gain a richer perspective on the underlying data's behavior and characteristics, allowing for more informed decision-making processes. Understanding these higher moments is essential for accurately interpreting and analyzing the distribution's shape and variability, ultimately enhancing the overall statistical analysis. The moment generating function (MGF) of a Poisson random variable X with parameter λ is given by:

$$M_X(t) = E(e^{tX}) = \exp(\lambda (e^t - 1))$$

(c) Cumulative Distribution Function

In probability theory, the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) $F(x)$ of a discrete random variable X provides a crucial framework for understanding the distribution of possible outcomes. It is essentially a mathematical representation that assigns a probability to each value that the random variable can take on. The CDF offers a unified way to quantify the likelihood of observing specific events within the sample space, encapsulating the probabilities of all values less than or equal to a particular point x . By defining the CDF in this manner, statisticians can analyze the behavior and characteristics of discrete random variables, which are variables that can only take on a countable number of different values. The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the Poisson distribution can be expressed as the sum of the probabilities from 0 to k :

$$F(k; \lambda) = P(X \leq k) = \sum_{i=0}^k \frac{\lambda^i e^{-\lambda}}{i!}$$

(d) Additivity

In the context of probability theory, the Poisson distribution plays a key role due to its unique characteristics and practical applications in modeling various real-world phenomena. The parameter of the resulting Poisson distribution, governing the combined random variable $X_1 + X_2$, is simply the summation of the individual parameters λ_1 and λ_2 . This mathematical relationship allows us to predict and analyze the behavior of the joint variable $X_1 + X_2$ with a high degree of accuracy, based on the knowledge of the original independent variables X_1 and X_2 . By understanding how the properties of Poisson distributions interact and transform when multiple random variables are involved, statisticians and researchers can gain valuable insights into complex systems and processes. If X_1 and X_2 are independent Poisson random variables with parameters λ_1 and λ_2 respectively, then their sum $X = X_1 + X_2$ is also a Poisson random variable with parameter $\lambda = \lambda_1 + \lambda_2$: $X \sim \text{Poisson}(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)$

(e) Lack of Memory

The Poisson distribution, a mathematical concept frequently used to model events with a known constant rate, possesses a unique statistical property known as the lack of memory property. This property, fundamental to understanding the behavior of Poisson processes, signifies that the occurrence of an event in the future within the Poisson framework is not influenced by past events. In simpler terms, the probability of an event happening at a specific point in time remains constant, independent of whether previous events have occurred or not. The Poisson distribution exhibits the lack of memory property, which means that the probability of an event occurring in the future is independent of the past events, given the rate λ remains constant.[5]

V VERIFICATION OF REAL LIFE EXAMPLES OF POISSON DISTRIBUTION

Activity: Car Accidents

Problem: On average, there are 4 car accidents per month at a certain intersection. What is the probability of having 6 accidents in a month?

Solution: $\lambda=4, k=6$

$$P(X = 6) = \frac{e^{-4}4^6}{6!} = \frac{e^{-4} \cdot 4096}{720} \approx 0.1042$$

VERIFICATION Step 1: Collect Real Data

Let's say we collect data for 12 months, and the number of car accidents per month at the intersection is as follows:(data from lifecare hospital Doraha)

• January: 5 accidents	• February: 3 accidents
• March: 4 accidents	• April: 6 accidents
• May: 3 accidents	• June: 4 accidents
• July: 5 accidents	• August: 3 accidents
• September: 4 accidents	• October: 7 accidents
• November: 2 accidents	• December: 4 accidents

4.3: Car Accidents

Step 2: Calculate the Average Rate (λ)

Calculate the average number of accidents per month (λ):

$$\lambda = \frac{5+3+4+6+3+4+5+3+4+7+2+4}{12} \approx 4.17$$

Step 3: Compare Observed and Expected Frequencies

Poisson Formula: $P(X = k) = \frac{e^{-\lambda}\lambda^k}{k!}$

For $\lambda=4.17$, calculate the probability of having exactly 6 accidents in a month:

$$P(X = 6) = \frac{e^{-4.17}4.17^6}{6!} = \frac{e^{-4.17} \times 6564.34}{720} \approx 0.1226$$

Expected Frequency: Multiply the probability by the total number of months to get the expected number of months with exactly 6 accidents:

$$\text{Expected frequency} = P(X = 6) \cdot \text{Total number of months} = 0.1226 \cdot 12 = 1.471$$

Observed Frequency: Count the actual number of months with exactly 6 accidents in the collected data. In our data set, one month had exactly 6 accidents.

VI CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the verification of the Poisson probability distribution using real-life examples underscores its efficacy and practical utility in modeling discrete events that occur independently and at a constant average rate. This statistical model proves particularly valuable in various fields like manufacturing for defect counts and traffic management for accident frequencies at intersections. Through detailed statistical analyses, such as comparing observed mean and variance to theoretical expectations, the consistency in accuracy showcased by the Poisson model across diverse real-world scenarios solidifies its reputation as a reliable tool for effectively predicting and analyzing random events across different contexts.

This alignment demonstrates the practical utility of the Poisson distribution when it comes to accurately forecasting event frequencies and comprehending their fluctuations. Such insights prove invaluable in enhancing decision-making processes and optimizing resource allocation dynamics across diverse sectors like quality control and traffic management. Despite its practical significance, the validation process also underscores the critical nature of acknowledging and evaluating the foundational assumptions underlying the Poisson model. In real-world scenarios, deviations like temporal or spatial interdependencies, as well as fluctuations in occurrence rates, can challenge the model's predictive accuracy, prompting the need for tailored adjustments or the exploration of alternative methodologies to ensure precision and reliability. Overall, the successful verification of the Poisson distribution in diverse contexts confirms its value as a powerful tool for probabilistic modeling. It provides researchers and practitioners with reliable insights into the nature of random events, enhancing operational efficiencies and risk management strategies across various applications.

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